

The Effectiveness of Human Formation of Maradjao Magbalantay College Seminary as Perceived by the Seminarians

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Abstract

The seminary formation is composed of four aspects: human, spiritual, intellectual and pastoral. Seminarian is educated and prepared for the priesthood through preparation and practice, field education, spiritual instruction, retreats, seminars, and community life. This study thus aimed to determine the Effectiveness of Human Formation of Maradjao Magbalantay College Seminary as perceived by the Seminarians. This study utilized the research method descriptive-survey with 32 participants and a total Maradjao Magbalantay College Seminary population. The main tool used in gathering the requisite data was a questionnaire made by the researcher. The data collected were treated using frequency count and percentage distribution descriptive statistical tools, mean and standard deviation, and variance analysis (ANOVA). In general, there was no significant difference in the effectiveness of the Seminary Formation to the Seminarians of Maradjao Magbalantay College Seminary when grouped according to the profile variable, age. On the other hand, the stage in seminary under the variable Formation of Conscience shown that there was significant difference as to the effectiveness of the Human Formation. With the collected results, the researcher recommended that the formators should be more observant to the seminarians in the community life. Same as to the seminarians, they should be more faithful and devoted to their vocation.

Keywords: *trials, possibilities, situations, seminary, formation.*

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Introduction

The formation of seminaries is dedicated to fostering the development of discernment and the growth of vocation, particularly in the ministry of priesthood. According to Richard Gula, ministers are expected to embody generosity as a practice of Christian Charity. They are expected to be magnanimous, making themselves available to others and being willing to go the extra mile (Gula, 2013).

A prospective priest must have an open heart to pain, poverty, and happiness, enabling them to embrace individuals who are suffering. Pope Francis emphasizes that ministers should be clothed with weakness, enabling them to feel sympathy for others in ignorance and error.

Cardinal Rosales' quote, "Gawin munang Tao, bago gawing Pari," encourages religious and diocesan seminarians and formators to prioritize human formation. This process shapes seminarians' awareness of their actions, holding them responsible for the consequences. Human formation helps seminarians differentiate between right and wrong, emphasizing a priest's love for humanity or "mankind" to be "maka-tao" through Charism.

However, some seminarians seek conveniences in life, developing unhealthy attitudes towards wealth and money, influenced by the elevated status attributed to priests and seminarians by culture. Young individuals, including seminarians, may succumb to the impact of multimedia and consumer propaganda, adopting fashionable concepts and lifestyles devoid of values. Manifestations of immaturity in seminary life include the prolongation of adolescent tastes and desires, a tendency towards various types of addiction, mediocrity, minimalism, a lack of decisiveness, and slow internalization of values. According to the CBCP, these issues can seriously affect the motivation of seminarians.

In the 2017-2018 academic year at Maradjao Magbalantay College Seminary, 10 out of 41 seminarians were expelled due to violations against the formation, while three others voluntarily left due to personal issues that interrupted their training. The researcher aimed to assess the effectiveness of Human Formation at Maradjao Magbalantay College Seminary, as perceived by the seminarians, to provide a basis for proposed recommendations.

Materials and Methods

The study made use of the descriptive research design applying survey technique. The design of the study was considered appropriate because it investigated a present situation. Specially, the study focused in determining the effectiveness of human formation of Maradjao Magbalantay College Seminary.

The research respondents were all seminarians of Maradjao Magbalantay College Seminary, with a total population of thirty two (32). The study used a researcher-made questionnaire to gather data. The questionnaire consists of two parts: Part I was the profile respondent; Part II was the effectiveness of human formation of Maradjao Magbalantay College Seminary. This instrument was presented to the experts for content and face validation. The corrections were reflected before the administration of the instrument.

The researcher made a letter of request asking to the Seminary Rector to conduct the study signed by the researcher's adviser. Then, the researcher made a letter also to the

participants asking permission to conduct the study, and after their approval, it was distributed to the seminarians of Maradjao Magbalantay College Seminary. When the consent was given, the researchers disseminated the questionnaires to the participants personally. After gathering the necessary information, the data were tallied, scored, analyzed and interpreted.

In this study, various statistical tools were applied to comprehensively assess and understand the characteristics and effectiveness of human formation at Maradjao Magbalantay College Seminary. Frequency count and percentage distribution were utilized to establish the demographic profile of participants, specifically focusing on age and length of stay in the seminary. Mean and Standard Deviation analyses were employed to gauge the extent of human formation across multiple dimensions, including obedience and discipline, conscience formation, physical-emotional-sexual-relational integrity, and lifestyle simplicity. The Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) served as a crucial tool in discerning any significant differences in the effectiveness of human formation concerning the profile of the participants, providing a comprehensive framework for evaluating the overall impact of the seminary's programs on its seminarians.

Results

Profile of the Participants

Table 1. Distribution of Participants According to Demographic Profile

Profile	Variables	f (n=32)	%
Age	16 years old	2	6.25%
	17 years old	3	9.37%
	18 years old	10	31.25%
	19 years old and above	17	53.13%
Stages in Seminary	Propaedeutic Stage	16	50%
	Discipleship Stage	16	50%

As shown in Table 1, there are 17 (53.13%) who are composed of 19 years old and above; 10 (31.25%) are 18 years old; 3 (9.37%) are 17 years old and 2 (6.25%) who belong to 16 years old. This indicated that majority of the participants fell on the age of 19 years old and above. In terms to their stages in the seminary, there were 16 (50%) who belong to propaedeutic stage and 16 (50%) belonged discipleship stage.

Table 2. The Effectiveness of the Human Formation to the Seminarians of Maradjao Magbalantay College Seminary as perceived by the Participants in terms of Obedience and Discipline

Obedience and Discipline	Mean	SD	VI
1. Spiritual direction helps me realize that obedience to formation is obedience to God.	4.44	0.72	Extremely Effective
2. Team building helps me establish good leadership skills.	4.03	0.78	Very Effective
3. Seminary Daily schedule helps me become obedient and disciplined.	4.25	0.67	Very Effective
4. Individual colloquium helps me accept and respect correction from my formators.	4.38	0.71	Extremely Effective

5. Being in community helps me become responsible in my behavior.	4.44	0.80	Extremely Effective
Average	4.31	0.47	Extremely Effective

Legend:

Scale	Parameter	Verbal Interpretation (VI)
1	1.00 – 1.79	Not Effective
2	1.80 – 2.59	Somewhat Effective
3	2.60 – 3.39	Effective
4	3.40 – 4.29	Very Effective
5	4.30 – 5.00	Extremely Effective

Table 2 shows the results on survey questionnaire given to the participants. In terms of the variable *Obedience and Discipline*, the Statement 1, “*Spiritual direction helps me realize that obedience to formation is obedience to God,*” and statement 5, “*Being in community helps me accept and respect correction from my formators,*” got mean results of ($M= 4.44$; $SD= 0.80$) and ($M= 4.44$; $SD=0.72$) and both have verbal interpretation of *Extremely Effective*. This implies that Spiritual Direction was extremely effective to the human formation of Maradjao Magbalantay College Seminary and the director was a friend who helps lead seminarians to hear God's voice. A Spiritual Director is a mentor who understands the Church's teachings and also gives guidance to seminarians through their faithful observance. In addition, being in the community encourages seminarians to be mindful of his actions. According to the word of William that one can engage in such conversation in order to help another to develop a right conscience, to understand the meaning of a particular doctrine or religious practice, and to learn how to perform a particular ritual.

More so, Statement 4, “*Individual colloquium helps me accept and respect correction from my formators,*” “*Seminary Daily schedule helps me become obedient and discipline,*” and “*Team building helps me establish good leadership skills*” are rated by the participants with mean of ($M= 4.38$; $SD 0.7$) and ($M=4.25$; $SD= 0.67$) respectively.

However, in Statement 2, “*Team Building helps me establish good leadership skill*” got the mean of ($M=4.44$; $SD= 0.80$) with verbal interpretation of *Very Effective*. Meaning to say, even if it was rated as the lowest indicator, the team building activity of Seminarians was very effective in behavioral improvement and on developing leadership skills. As Vocation Centre stressed that seminarians observe community life, as brothers in Christ, serving, learning, praying together and sharing meals and leisure time, they can play sports, work out, read, or visit friends and family in their spare time, the bonds they share with each other, as they journey towards the priesthood, are a great source of joy, support and encouragement.

In general, as perceived by the participants, the variable *Obedience and Discipline* got an average mean of 4.22 and the standard deviation of 0.47 with verbal interpretation of *Extremely Effective*. The data revealed that the *Obedience and Discipline* of the human formation of Maradjao Mabalantay College Seminary manifested a very effective rate as to the values and virtues of human formation. The result also indicated that the Maradjao Magbalantay College Seminary Human Formation helped seminarians to comply with instructions, legislation or adherence to formation. Additionally, in doing things that take commitment and self-control brought were complied. Safa Mahzari

stated that it was distinguished clearly the difference from discipline to obedience. Being obedient is outsourcing the way one thinks, accepting too much life as rigid, or fixed, or given. Discipline, on the other hand, obeys what one wants. Doing the things, the person wants requires effort, as he always disagree with what those around him want for himself. As *Precis of Official Catholic Teaching* reminder on Obedience that it is always be a sacrifice; yet a joy, for it is a way of loving God.

Table 3. The Effectiveness of Human Formation to the Seminarians of Maradjao Magbalantay College Seminary as perceived by Participants in terms of A Lifestyle of Simplicity

A Lifestyle of Simplicity	Mean	SD	VI
1. Manualia helps me realize the importance of valuing things that are not mine.	3.63	0.91	Very Effective
2. Business level helps me appreciate the responsibility given to me as stewards of seminary properties.	3.72	1.05	Very Effective
3. Being in community helps me enjoy a simple life without looking for material things as Jesus is my example.	4.13	1.01	Very Effective
4. Recreation helps me detach from gadgets like cellphone.	3.91	1.00	Very Effective
5. The seminary's rule on gadgets teaches me to value simplicity	4.03	0.86	Very Effective
Average	3.88	0.59	Very Effective

Legend:

Scale	Parameter	Verbal Interpretation (VI)
1	1.00 – 1.79	Not Effective
2	1.80 – 2.59	Somewhat Effective
3	2.60 – 3.39	Effective
4	3.40 – 4.29	Very Effective
5	4.30 – 5.00	Extremely Effective

Table 3 shows the variable being deliberated in this study which is the *A Lifestyle of Simplicity*. The outcome does mean that the daily routine and the way of that Maradjao Magbalantay Collge Seminary help seminarians to be satisfied from having less in make use of available. The seminarians valued the facilities, both material and institutional, which the seminary provides for the community in order to fulfill a relational responsibility that they all have to take care of, and this is simplicity, of certain values that they share.

A Lifestyle of Simplicity refers to the simple living of seminarians. The spirit of self—sacrifice must be inculcated according to CBCP, hence, expressing itself in the appreciation of the dignity of manual work in the courageous solution of life's pains and challenges, and the joyful acceptance of difficulties. Seminary formation instills a good feeling of value among seminarians that does not rely on what they have. The first and most efficient simplicity of source is our bad yet graceful humanity's joyful embrace.

In addition, under the variable A Lifestyle of Simplicity, Statement 3, “*Being in community helps me enjoy a simple life without looking for material things as Jesus is my example*” got the mean of (M= 4.13; SD= 1.01) with verbal interpretation of *Very Effective*. This goes to

say that the community of Maradjao Magbalantay College Seminary lived a simple yet blessed and joyful life. The community of seminarians encourages each seminarians to live in joy of devotion to Jesus Christ and the delights are true with genuine happiness of a community who are earnestly pursuing priesthood together, and trying to become God’s men. The Seminarians’ experiences are simple that is in Jesus. In connection to Ratio Fundamentalis Institutionis Sacerdotalis, it suggested that seminarians are obligated to show, both individually and as a group, that they have initialized an authentically priestly way of life, in modesty and in the service of their brethren, and not only in their outward behavior.

Furthermore, in the Statement 5, “*The seminary’s rule on gadgets teaches me to value simplicity,*” “*Recreation helps me detach from gadgets like cellphone,*” and “*Business level helps me appreciate the responsibility given to me as stewards of seminary properties*” got the mean of (M= 4.03; SD= 0.86), (M=3.91; SD= 1.00) and (M= 3.72; SD= 1.05) respectfully.

However, in Statement 1, “*Manualia helps me realize the importance of valuing things that are not mine*” got the lowest mean with (M= 3.63; SD= 0.91) and verbally interpreted as *Very Effective*. Significance of Manualia of Maradjao Magbalantay College Seminary is to train the seminarians to be independent and to be disciplined and it help the seminarian realize and value of service. All of these are parts of his formation to become a better person one day. Perhaps, other aspects of human development according to Fr. Stephen include the everyday life behaviors, the seminary addresses cleaning, washing, eating, personal hygiene, etiquette, fitness, etc., and all the qualities expected of any adaptable and genuinely human citizen. In Seminarians Handbook, it was clear that seminarian has an assignment of stewardship, to which he should devote himself.

Comprehensively, the *A Lifestyle of Simplicity* got an average of 3.88 with standard deviation of 0.59 and verbally interpreted as *Very Affective*. The data exposed that the A Lifestyle with Simplicity, values and virtue of Human Formation of Maradjao Magbalantay College Seminary revealed a very effective as to human formations of seminarians. CBCP commission on seminaries stresses that simplicity growth does not imply hatred of products and creation, seminary formation seeks to create a real appreciation for development in the seminarians, an appreciation that enables them to respect it and to care for it is the gift of God. Through a life of joyful and fruitful simplicity, priest can best testify to him.

Table 4 shows the effectiveness of the human formation to the seminarians of Maradjao Magbalantay College Seminary as perceived by the participants in terms of formation of conscience. Statement 1, “*Spiritual direction helps listen to the inner voice of God*” got the mean of (M= 4.44; SD= 0.62) with verbal interpretation of *Extremely Effective*. This indicated that after Spiritual Direction, the seminarians of Maradjao Magbalantay College seminary experience healing, consolation and enlightenment. Just as CBCP said seminary formation has to cope with seminarians forming an upright consciousness.

Table 4. The Effectiveness of the Human Formation to the Seminarians of Maradjao Magbalantay College Seminary as perceived by the Participants in terms of Formation of Conscience

Formation of Conscience	Mean	SD	VI
1. Spiritual direction help listen to the inner voice of God.	4.44	0.62	Extremely Effective

2. My brother seminarians help me to correct my mistakes and to avoid bad doings.	3.74	0.83	Very Effective
3. The homilies of my formators help me develop my conscience.	4.19	0.78	Very Effective
4. Spiritual level opens my eyes from the truth, helps me value it more, and abhor lies.	4.00	0.77	Very Effective
5. Peer evaluation helps me to become aware of my failures from the observations of my brother seminarians	3.88	1.18	Very Effective
Average	4.00	0.49	Very Effective

Legend:

Scale	Parameter	Verbal Interpretation (VI)
1	1.00 – 1.79	Not Effective
2	1.80 – 2.59	Somewhat Effective
3	2.60 – 3.39	Effective
4	3.40 – 4.29	Very Effective
5	4.30 – 5.00	Extremely Effective

Moreover, Statement 3: “*The homilies of my formators help me develop my conscience,*” Statement 4: “*Spiritual level opens my eyes from the truth, helps me value it more, and abhor lies,*” and ,” Statement 5: “*Peer evaluation helps me to become aware of my failures from the observations of my brother seminarians*” got mean results of ($M=4.19$; $SD=0.78$), ($M=4.00$; $SD= 0.77$) and ($M=3.88$; $SD= 1.18$). While, Statement 2: “*My brother seminarians helps me to correct my mistakes and to avoid bad doings,*” got the lowest mean of ($M=3.74$; $SD= 0.83$) and verbally described as *Very Effective*. The results showed that brotherly correction helps seminarian in choosing what is good and avoid what is bad. As Pope John Paul II suggests in *Pastores dabo Vobis*, seminarians need to be learned to love the truth, to be faithful, to love each person, to get a sense of justice, to be honest and responsible, to be sincerely humanitarian, to be men of honesty and, in particular, to be reasonable in judgment and behavior.

In general, the *Formation of Conscience* got an average mean of 4.00 and it got the standard deviation of 0.49 with verbal interpretation of *Very Effective*. The data presented that the *Conscience Formation* of Human Formation revealed that it was a very effective as to the values and virtues of Human Formation of Maradjao Magbalantay College Seminary. The results showed that the Seminarians had a well formed practical reason that helped them to recognize and seek what is good and to reject what is evil. They are conscious of the social environment and had enhanced the social interaction ability so that they can contribute to constructing the community he lives in. Ratio Fundamentalism Institutionis Sacerdotalis stresses that it is connected in the moral sphere with the demands that the seminarian slowly arrive at a well-formed consciousness, this means that he should be able to make the right decisions, endowed with sound judgment and able to have an unbiased view of people and events. And, according to CBCP that a seminarian may be a loss in determining what is right, good, and just, guided by the Sacred Scriptures and the Church's teaching, learning to follow the inner law that is God's voice within.

Table 5. The Effectiveness of the Human Formation to the Seminarians of Maradjao Magbalantay College Seminary as perceived by the Participants in terms of Physical-Emotional-Sexual- Relational Integrity

Physical-Emotional-Sexual- Relational Integrity	Mean	SD	VI
1. Investiture helps me appreciate chastity as a virtue and a gift from God	4.31	0.72	Extremely Effective
2. Sports help me to avoid pornography.	4.00	1.02	Very Effective
3. The formators celibate living helps me realize the importance of renouncing anything that is a threat to celibacy, vigilant over both body and spirit, high self-esteem and respect in intrapersonal relationship between men and women.	4.09	0.78	Very Effective
4. The seminary rule of not allowing seminarians to engage into exclusive relationship helps me appreciate celibacy.	3.91	0.89	Very Effective
5. Catechism helps me understand the boundaries towards opposite sex.	3.88	1.07	Very Effective
Average	4.04	1.07	Very Effective

Legend:

Scale	Parameter	Verbal Interpretation (VI)
1	1.00 – 1.79	Not Effective
2	1.80 – 2.59	Somewhat Effective
3	2.60 – 3.39	Effective
4	3.40 – 4 .29	Very Effective
5	4.30 – 5.00	Extremely Effective

As shown in Table 5, under the variable on *Physical-Emotional-Sexual- Relational Integrity*, Statement 1: “*Investiture helps me appreciate chastity as a virtue and a gift from God*” got the highest mean with (M=4.31; SD=0.72) and verbal interpretation of *Extremely Effective*. Meaning, the Investiture of cassock was effective in human formation of the seminarians as it helped seminarians to value priestly vows. Formation makes it clear to future priests or seminarians that the Church has required priests’ celibacy, calling it a “spiritual gift.” St Francis Xavier Major Seminary reminded the seminarians that investiture of the cassock represents the next stage of their formation process for the seminarians; and, the Catholic Church's Catechism said chastity is a moral good. It is also a blessing from heaven, a grace and a fruit of divine endeavor.

In addition, Statement 4: “*The seminary rule of not allowing seminarians to engage into exclusive relationship helps me appreciate celibacy*”, Statement 2, “*Sports helps me to avoid pornography,*” and Statement 3: “*The formators celibate living helps me realize the importance of renouncing anything that is a threat to celibacy, vigilant over both body and spirit, high self-esteem and respect in intrapersonal relationship between men and women*” got mean results of (M=3.91; SD=0.89), (M= 4.00; SD= 1.02) and (M= 4.09; SD= 0.78) reverently.

Meanwhile, Statement 5: “*Catechism helps me understand the boundaries towards opposite sex*” got the lowest mean of (M=3.88; SD= 1.07) with verbal description of *Very Effective*. This described that Catechism was very affective on reminding seminarians the boundaries towards opposite sex. The Ratio Fundamentalism Institutionis Sacerdotalis pressures that it would be appropriate to take into account the relationship between the seminarian and the woman as discussed in the teaching papers in which they read and that it affects the seminarians in the sphere of life.

Table 6. The Summary of the Average of All Variables with the Mean

Variable	Mean	SD	VI
Obedience and Discipline	4.31	0.47	Very Effective
A Lifestyle of Simplicity	3.88	0.59	Very Effective
Formation of Conscience	4.00	0.49	Very Effective
Physical-Emotional-Sexual- Relational Integrity	4.04	1.07	Very Effective
Grand Mean	4.03	0.44	Very Effective

Legend:

Scale	Parameter	Verbal Interpretation (VI)
1	1.00 – 1.79	Not Effective
2	1.80 – 2.59	Somewhat Effective
3	2.60 – 3.39	Effective
4	3.40 – 4.29	Very Effective
5	4.30 – 5.00	Extremely Effective

Table 6 shows the summary of the average mean of all variables. It can be gleaned from the table that among the variables indicated above, the *Obedience and Discipline* got the mean of (M=4.31; SD = 0.47) with verbal interpretation of *Very Effective*. This means that the Seminarians of Maradjaw Magbalantay College Seminary learned how to trustfully respond to figures of authority. The authoritative hang-ups are addressed in ways that would allow a seminarian to relax with their Formator without giving up on discipline. Obedience and Discipline are important because one of the evangelical counsels is the Obedience and of the evangelical counsels required discipline. Fr. Andy Lubi said that the seminary must then grant a well-defined life program that is essential and relevant, an atmosphere of silence and discipline is an essential component because it encourages self-introspection, continuous adjustment to divine inspiration, prudent use of liberty, private and communal harmony and coherence.

The variable, *Physical-Emotional-Sexual- Relational Integrity*, ranked as the second highest which got a mean of (M=4.04; SD=1.07). It was reflected that the Physical-Emotional-Sexual- Relational Integrity virtue and values of human formation of Maradjaw Magbalantay College Seminary was *Very Effective*. In the seminary, the seminarians were thought to value the beauty of chastity and celibacy, through the help of human formation, they grow in genuine respect for women whom they can maturely relate. According to Pope John Paul II stated that human formation molds seminarians in love which involved the whole person in all its aspects-physical, psychological and spiritual and which was expressed in the "nuptial context" of the human body, in which an individual gives himself to another and takes the other to himself, a well-known sex education.

In addition, the third variable, *Formation of Conscience*, got a mean of (M=4.00; SD=0.49) and verbally interpreted as *Extremely Effective*. The seminary offered a curriculum, like spiritual direction, peer evaluation, retreats and many others that help seminarians develop their inner knowledge of the moral goodness and of seminarian's actions with a sense of responsibility to do right or be decent. Moral conscience advises a person to "do well and escape bad;" it also judges individual decisions, endorses good ones and disapproves evil ones. The dignity of the human being implies and includes uprightness of moral conscience, according to the Catholic Church's Catechism.

Conscious experience reflects the level of the principles of morality; their implementation by practical discernment of reasons and goods in the present situation; and, finally, judgment on concrete acts that are yet to be performed or already performed.

The last ranked variable, *A Lifestyle of Simplicity*, got the mean of (M=3.33; SD = 0.59) with verbal interpretation of *Very Effective*. Living and embracing the simple living, seminarians develop their chaste of love to the people around them, the formation indeed molds seminarians to be grateful and satisfied of what the seminary provide for them as they are taught to value common good. As Richard Foster said Christian simplicity is not just a faddish effort to react to the chaotic and materialistic world we find ourselves in; it is a call to obey Christ for every Christian of every generation.

Table 7. Significant Difference between the Effectiveness of the Human Formation Program to the Seminarians of Maradjao Magbalantay College Seminary when grouped According to the Profile Variable

Human Formation Program Component	Age			Seminary's Stage		
	df	P-value	Decision	df	p-value	Decision
Obedience and Discipline	14.55	0.93	Accept	3.13	0.51	Accept
A Lifestyle of Simplicity	1.17	0.33	Accept	0.42	0.51	Accept
Formation of Conscience	0.29	0.50	Accept	6.86	0.01	Reject
Physical-Emotional-Sexual-Relational Integrity	0.60	0.62	Accept	0.05	0.81	Accept

As expressed in the tabular analysis on the variable, *Human Development*, the p-value of age is 0.93 and the p-value of stage in seminary is 0.51. Therefore, the two variables, namely: age and length of seminar stayed should not be rejected as their p-value was higher than the significance point of 0.05. In other words, there is no significant difference in the age and stage in seminary when it came to the Effectiveness of the Human Formation Maradjao Magbalantay College Seminary with regards to *Obedience and Discipline*. Pope John Paul II in *Pastores Dabo Vobis*, wrote: “Affective maturity, which is the product of an education in real and responsible love, is an important and critical element in the development of priesthood candidates.”

With these, it could be gleaned that in Table 7, with the *A Lifestyle of Simplicity* variable, the p-value of *age* is 0.33 and the p-value of stage in *seminary* is 0.51. Therefore, the two factors, *age* and *length of stay in the seminary*, should not be rejected because their p-value is higher than the level of significance which is 0.05. This means that the factors, *age* and *stage in seminary*, of the participants had no significant difference when it comes to the effectiveness of the Human Formation to the Seminarians of Maradjao Magbalantay College Seminary as to *A Lifestyle of Simplicity*.

In addition, the variable, *Formation of Consciousness*, got the p-value of 0.50 in terms of age as this means that the p-value of age was higher than the significance point of 0.05; therefore, the null hypothesis should not be rejected. In contrast, as to the stage in seminary formation, it should be rejected because of the p-value 0.01 which is lower than the level of significance. Meaning, there was a significant difference as to the stage of the seminary formation in the variable Formation of Consciousness. Propaedeutic stage is the stage when the seminarians are in one to two years at the seminary

formation, while the discipleship stage is when the seminarians are in the formation for three to five years, and both have different programs.

According to Gerard J. McGlone, SJ, and Len Sperry that a seminarian who is relatively young and therefore within a specific age of development would have a quantitatively different integration of human, spiritual, intellectual and pastoral experience than a relative older person.

As shown in Table 7, the p-value of age in Physical-Emotional-Sexual- Relational Integrity got the o-value of 0.62; while the stage in seminary formation got the p-value of 0.81. The decision of the null hypothesis for the two factors: age and length of stay in the seminary, were not rejected because both of its p-values were higher than the 0.05 level of significance. This means that the participants' age and stage in seminary formation have no statistical significant in terms of the effectiveness of human formation for the seminarians of Maradjao Magbalantay College Seminary with regards to Physical-Emotional-Sexual- Relational Integrity.

Conclusions and Recommendations

From the established findings above, some conclusions were drawn:

Most of the seminarians of Maradjao Magbalantay College Seminary were 19 year old and above. As to stages in the seminary formation, both had an equal number of seminarian, 16 (50%) were at propaedeutic stage; while, 16 (50%) were at discipleship stage.

The Obedience and Discipline variables got the highest degree of control in terms of human formation of the seminarians. With the average mean of 4.22, and the standard deviation of 0.47, the participants of Maradjao Magbalantay College Seminarians agreed that the Obedience and Discipline of human formation was Extremely Effective and this served as one of the foundations in the seminary life growth.

In general, there was no significant difference in the effectiveness of the Human Formation to the Seminarians of Maradjao Magbalantay College Seminary when grouped according to the profile variable, age, because it was reflected on its over-all p-value that was higher than the 0.05 level of significance. The said profile variables, therefore, did not affect the effectiveness of the human formation of the seminarians of Maradjao Magbalantay College Seminary. On the other hand, the p-value of stage in seminary under the variable Formation of Conscience was lower than the 0.05 level of significance which means that there was significant difference as to the effectiveness of the human Formation of the Seminarians of Maradjao Magbalantay College Seminary. This means that the seminarians' stage in seminary had an impact on their development in the seminary as well as on their understanding of the structure of the said formation

In the light of the findings and conclusions, the following were recommended:

The Formators of Maradjao Magbalantay College Seminary may assign one Formator during manualia to accompany seminarians, to make an environment not just clean but that favors friendship and fraternity, to allow seminarians to improve relations with formators and co-seminarians and value the dignity of manual labour. Accompanying seminarians during manualia help seminarians develop into healthy, well-balanced individuals who can relate to all kinds of people and show good personal qualities such as empathy, flexibility, devotion and organizational skills.

The seminarians of the propaedeutic stage may zealously pay attention to their spiritual director and formator's fraternal advices, so that they may build the capacity to adapt and grow in different situations and they may be open to formators and co-seminarians with any questions or issues they might have, so that formators and co-seminarians may fix them as early as possible.

Since the study is about seminary formation, a study aligned from the present study could be performed by future researchers. They may be conduct on what factors could affect the community life of the seminarians as their research subject.

Conflict of interests

No conflict of interest.

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